

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF SEVERAL COUNTRIES ON THE WAY OF SETTLEMENT OF THE NAGORNO-KARABAKH CONFLICT

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Abstract

The resolution of Nagorno-Karabakh conflict was supposed to create new geopolitical realities in the South Caucasus region and in the post-Soviet space as a whole.

It was important for extra-regional forces, in the event of a settlement of the problem around Nagorno-Karabakh, to use the created situation to their advantage, not allowing the victorious country to strengthen, but most importantly, to contribute to the weakening of Russia's role in post-imperial countries.

Keywords: Nagorno-Karabakh conflict, geopolitics, farsighted policy, interaction

Purpose of Research. The dominance of the OSCE Minsk Group co-chair countries' own ambitions, an attempt to disrupt the political, economic and military development of the Republic of Azerbaijan did not provide an opportunity to facilitate the peaceful settlement of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict.

Based on the above, it becomes absolutely clear that the OSCE Minsk Group co-chairs did not want the Armenian-Azerbaijani Nagorno-Karabakh conflict to be resolved peacefully or militarily.

The resolution of the problem could lead to the natural loss of positions of the Russian Federation, the USA, and France in the South Caucasus.

But on the other hand, Türkiye's growing interest in the problem around Nagorno-Karabakh made worry the Minsk Group co-chairing countries, because they could lose their positions in the South Caucasus. The activation of Türkiye's diplomacy, rapprochement with Azerbaijan expanded Türkiye's participation in the process of resolving the conflict and establishing the territorial integrity of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Research Methodology. The methodological and theoretical basis of this paper were articles, Internet resources touching upon the foreign policy aspects of Azerbaijan, Türkiye and other countries at the present stage, as well as a deep analysis of the author.

Scientific novelty. Nagorno-Karabakh conflict and the ways to resolve its problem studied in all aspects. Its first paper reveals in detail prospects for the settlement of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict for leading forces in the world.

The signing of the 'Contract of the Century' (September 1994) increased the West's interest in the region and consequently intensified its engagement in the conflict resolution giving the new momentum to the peace process via CSCE mediation [p.79].¹

The ineffective activities of the OSCE Minsk Group co-chair countries to resolve the Nagorno-

Karabakh problem led to closer alignment with the countries that faced aggressive policies.

For example, Georgia took a neutral position regarding the conflict around Nagorno-Karabakh. Therefore, official Tbilisi declared its desire to maintain friendly relations with both Armenia and Azerbaijan, and proposed to hold negotiations within the framework of the OSCE Minsk Group in Tbilisi. But the destructive position of Armenia showed itself in this direction.

After restoring its independence, Georgia faced the problem of separatism, which gave grounds for drawing analogies between Karabakh, Abkhazia and South Ossetia.

Also, many Turkish and Azerbaijani investments in the Georgian economy, for example, strengthening the position of Turkish business circles in Adjara, the spread of Islam - all this became an additional reason in the hands of the Armenian authorities to speak out against Azerbaijani-Georgian relations.

In January 2000, a meeting was held in Tbilisi with Georgian President Eduard Shevardnadze. As a result, the "Cooperation and Security Pact in the Caucasus" ("Tbilisi Pact") was signed. As a result of a farsighted policy, Azerbaijan joined the pact.

The protracted nature of peace negotiations and the deadlock created around the resolution of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict have led to an intensive rapprochement between the countries of the Turkic world in all directions.

Today, the integration process is receiving increasing support, and the idea of unifying Turkic countries frightens Western countries.

Since 1992, a summit of the states of Turkic languages has been held; in the same year of 1992, the United Administration of Turkic Arts and Languages was formed in Almaty, and in 1998, the Parliamentary Assembly of Turkic-Speaking Countries began operating in Baku.

¹ Garibov, A. OSCE and Conflict Resolution in the Post-Soviet Area: The Case of the Armenia-Azerbaijan Nagorno-Karabakh Conflict.

On August 22, 2012, Türkiye, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Azerbaijan adopted a single flag, and at the end of 2014, through the efforts of the Azerbaijani diaspora, the first regional diaspora office of the Turkic Council opened in Kyiv.²

It is indisputable that the support of the Turkic states for the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan and the process of peaceful settlement of the Armenian-Azerbaijani.

Nagorno-Karabakh conflict by peaceful means within the framework of the norms and principles of international law, the active Turkish and Kazakh mediation mission could not help but worry many, including the co-chair countries of the OSCE Minsk Group.

Azerbaijan's ties with the Arab and Muslim world subsequently played a decisive role in the process of restoring the country's territorial integrity. The policy of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev, which meets national interests, and the continuation of this policy by President İlham Aliyev led to the propaganda of Azerbaijan's objective position in the Armenian-Azerbaijani Nagorno-Karabakh conflict.

During the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict, the structure of the geopolitics of the South Caucasus was determined by a complex of internal and external factors, among which the strategic position and geopolitical significance of the region, the presence of territorial claims of certain states on their neighbors (Armenia and Azerbaijan) played a leading role.

The above circumstances make this region a center of intersection of strategic interests of the world's leading countries and major international organizations. Thus, among them were the USA, Russia, China, Iran, Türkiye, Israel, as well as regional organizations and associations such as NATO, OSCE, EU, etc.³

The problem around Nagorno-Karabakh gave everyone an idea of the interaction of regional and global powers in international mediation.

The policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan towards resolving the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict is a valuable example of the successful use of natural resources, diplomatic ties and the geopolitical position of the state in order to resolve and attract the interest of strong states to the process of resolving the conflict peacefully [c. 471].⁴

Unfortunately, in the modern political arena, international conflicts often lead to the formation of new un-

recognized states that make every effort to gain independence, relying on international law and the support of the patron state [c. 28].⁵

Therefore, it is imperative to separately consider the prospects for the OSCE Minsk Group co-chair countries in the process of resolving the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict, as the details of the expectations of each of these countries are revealed.

It should be taken into account that the OSCE Minsk Group co-chair countries had their own visions for resolving the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict.

For example, Russia, if the problem was resolved, wanted to maintain its dominance in political, military and economic initiatives throughout the region.

It was important for the Russian Federation to resolve the conflict without losing its lead and without allowing the US to become more involved in the region.

The prospects for Russia in the South Caucasus were vast. In addition to the above, there was a desire to use the region's trans communications.

In general, Azerbaijan is a natural barrier for Russia against threats from the South (from the Middle East, Central Asia and the Persian Gulf). Therefore, a stable and strong Azerbaijan is extremely important for Russia, otherwise the Russian Caucasus may face unpleasant destructive influences.⁶

Analyzing these nuances, we come to the conclusion that Russia should be interested in the South Caucasus, which is part of its strategic interests and necessary living space, always remaining a zone of peace and stability. At the same time, the policies of the South Caucasus states themselves have become more predictable for Russia.

In the near future, Russia should rely on socio-cultural factors, equal and mutually beneficial foundations that eliminate previous mistakes, and direct its finances and efforts to supporting the culture and historical traditions of the ethnic groups of the South Caucasus and Russia. Such values of foreign state policy can prevent disintegration and destructive processes.⁷

But, at the same time, it was necessary to preserve its own ambitions in the South Caucasus region by oppressing the interests of other states and maintaining the status quo around Nagorno-Karabakh. The US had an important interest and its own vision of the post-conflict period.

For example, the main thing for the official White House was not only the weakening of the Russian Fed-

² Шангараев Р. «Армия Турана» - проект Турции по военной интеграции тюркского мира. Угрозы и перспективы

URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/armiya-turana-proekt-turtsii-po-voennoy-integratsii-tyurkskogo-mira-ugrozy-i-perspektivy>

³ Гаджинская Н., Гаджинский Э. Дж. Геополитика в регионе Южного Кавказа на современном этапе и новая конфигурация политических сил

URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/geopolitika-v-regione-yuzhnogo-kavkaza-na-sovremennom-etape-i-novaya-konfiguratsiya-politicheskikh-sil>

⁴ Aliyeva-Mammadova, G. Interests and Azerbaijan's strategy in resolving the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict (1992-2012) // Universidad y Sociedad, 16 (S1), /p. 468-472

URL: <https://rus.ucf.edu.cu/index.php/rus/article/view/4728/4716>

⁵ Катков, А. Д. Проблема международного признания и феномен непризнанных государств в современном научном дискурсе

URL: <https://www.mid.ru/upload/medialibrary/901/Вестник%20№%203-2020.pdf#page=27>

⁶ Чернявский, С. Политика России на Южном Кавказе

URL: <https://www.viaevrasia.com/public/ru/политика-россии-на-южном-кавказе-станислав-чернявский.pdf>

⁷ Панов, И. А., Деметрадзе, М. Р., Шорохова, С. П. Южный Кавказ в современных геополитических реалиях Турции и России

URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/yuzhnyy-kavkaz-v-sovremennyh-geopoliticheskikh-realiyah-turtsii-i-rossii>

eration in the region, but also the intensive use of Azerbaijan's geopolitics for greater activation of its foreign policy concepts in all former Soviet republics, thereby affirming the postulates of a multipolar world as opposed to a unipolar one.

Based on this, the end of the ideological confrontation between the USSR and the USA led to the growth of American ambitions and attempts by official Washington to resolve regional conflicts. However, due to the lack of sufficient experience in conducting policy in the post-Soviet space, the USA began to approve of Turkey as a conductor of Western European ideas in the region of the South Caucasus and Central Asia.

By building friendly relations between post-Soviet states and Turkey, the United States attempted to reduce Russia's influence and then completely eliminate the presence of the Russian factor in these states.

Throughout history, France has had problems with Muslim countries and the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict is a strong indicator of this. The prospects for the increase in Islamophobia and Azerbaijanophobia for France were quite high, given the possibilities of settling the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict within the OSCE Minsk Group.

However, the well-thought-out policy of Azerbaijan has become a catalyst for the restoration of full sovereignty over its lands. The opening of the Zangezur corridor will further contribute to the creation of a multipolar world. In this regard, the Republic of Azerbaijan will continue to exert an ever-increasing influence on events in the region and beyond its borders.

Azerbaijan also paid attention to relations with European countries. On November 14, 2006, the EU-Azerbaijan Cooperation Action Plan came into force.

The EU expressed its consent to the peaceful settlement of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict by supporting the efforts of the OSCE Minsk Group and using the capabilities of the UN Security Council. All this contributed to strengthening the EU dialogue with states interested in the political settlement of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict and ensuring stability in the South Caucasus.

It is clear that European countries were additionally interested in establishing stability in the regions of the South Caucasus in order to advance their economic plans and maximize the use of the energy resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Europe realized that maximum rapprochement with Azerbaijan is possible only through assistance in the peaceful resolution of the conflict around Nagorno-Karabakh and the restoration of the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan.

Awareness of these facts was insufficient to establish peace in the region, since the application of double standards did not provide an opportunity for a real and objective acceleration of the peace negotiations process within the framework of the norms and principles of international law.

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), launched in 2013 by China's leadership to integrate the country into the Middle East and Europe, has made Azerbaijan even more important.

In the struggle for world leadership, China has strengthened its economic initiatives, which has resulted in the acceleration of economic integration of countries located along the Great Silk Road, including, naturally, Azerbaijan.

Therefore, the PRC has become one of the state's interested in resolving the conflict around Nagorno-Karabakh and establishing stability in the Caucasus in order to ensure its political interests.

Conclusion

Today, the Republic of Azerbaijan, as a result of a far-sighted policy, control of transport communications and energy resources, is becoming a state that shapes the geopolitics of the region. Depending on this, how deeply the world's power centers, including the Armenian government, will be able to assess the role and strengthening of Azerbaijan's position will depend on the nature of the processes in Eurasia.

Due to new challenges thrown at Azerbaijan by some Western countries, our state will continue the policy of developing the military sphere to fully ensure its security, and the process of the country's prosperity in all areas will also continue to further strengthen the strong status of the state of Azerbaijan in the South Caucasus region and far beyond its borders.

Predictions for future.

In the future, Azerbaijan will continue the policy of developing the military sphere to ensure its security, and the process of the country's prosperity in all spheres will also continue to further strengthen the country's strong status both in the South Caucasus region and throughout the world.

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